

Lemont has excellent grain quality.

Buli-INIA showed yield potential similar to that of check varieties in 13 regional trials in Chile during 1988-89 (see table).

Its growth duration is similar to Diamante's, but it has better tillering ability, shorter and stronger stems, a grain length:width > 3. and lower 1,000-grain weight.

Buli-INIA is resistant to lodging and tolerates low temperature (15-17 °C) better than Diamante and Oro. Head rice recovery is about 50%, eating quality is good.

V18, a promising new rice variety for the Red River Delta of Vietnam

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V18 is a promising, high-yielding, semidwarf rice (95-105 cm) with a high photosynthetic rate and high response to N. It was developed at INSA from IR8/Lomello/Lao Tim.

V18 matures in 180–185 d in dry season and 130–135 d in wet season. It has very good plant type: moderate tillering, late senescence, and erect, dark green leaves.

Grains are medium-size, translucent, and have good cooking quality. The 1,000-grain weight is 27g. High percentages of ripened grains, total milled rice, and head rice recovery characterized V18.

V18 has good seedling cold tolerance and is moderately resistant to major pests and diseases. It yielded 17% more than

Table 1. Performance of V18 in replicated yield trials in 1985-88 dry seasons.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (103/m ²)	Ripened grains (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Milling recovery (%)	Head rice (%)
<i>With 100 kg N/ha</i>							
V18	6.2	277	23	86	27	72	53
IR8	5.8	248	21	81	28	68	33
<i>With 200 kg N/ha</i>							
V18	7.5	311	28	85	27	-	-
IR8	6.4	288	23	75	28	-	-

Table 2. Performance of V18 at Dan phuong-Hanoi and Mo lao-Ha son binh, Vietnam, 1988-90 dry seasons.

Variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)				Increase (%)
	1988	1989	1990	Mean	
<i>Dan phuong</i>					
V18	5.3 (4.6)	6.4 (10)	6.1 (40)	6.1	13.3
IR8 (check)	4.1 (180)	5.8 (5.4)	5.7 (0.7)	5.4	
<i>Mo lao</i>					
V18		6.1 (7.2)	6.4 (18)	6.2	21.6
V14 (check)		5.0 (20)	5.3 (15)	5.1	

^a Figures in parentheses indicate area in ha.

check variety IR8 in research trials and 13.3–21.6% more in farmers' fields (Table 1, 2).

V18 was released for use in the highly

fertile soils of the Red River Delta. It is being tested on an estimated 1,000 ha in the delta. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

VL Dhan 221, a new upland rice variety for the northwestern Himalayan region of India

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Rice variety VL Dhan 221 was released in 1991 for upland kharif cultivation in UP and Himachal Pradesh (HP). Derived from IR2053/Ch 1039, VL Dhan 221 was developed through the pedigree method at ICAR from IRRI material.

VL Dhan 221 was tested in All India Coordinated Trials conducted at different sites in UP and HP. It yielded an average of 2.5 t/ha, 28.8% more than national check Bala and 31.5% more than the best qualifying genotype HPU2202 (Table 1).

VL Dhan 221 is semitall with compact and well-exserted panicles, good spikelet fertility, and awnless medium grains. It

matures in 110-115 d, tillers well, tolerates drought and low temperature fairly well, and resists leaf and neck blast and stem borer (Table 2).

Rice under rainfed upland conditions in UP hills was traditionally sown during Mar-Apr and remained in the field until Sep. Only three crops (spring rice - wheat - finger millet - fallow) could

Table 1. Yield performance of VL Dhan 221 in coordinated trials.^a UP and HP, India, 1985-87.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)				Superiority (%)
	1985 (4)	1986 (3)	1987 (4)	Av yield	
VL Dhan 221	2.9	2.8	1.7	2.5	
Bala (check)	2.2	2.2	1.4	1.9	28.8
HPU2202	2.4	2.3	1.1	1.9	31.5

^a Figures in parentheses indicate number of locations.

Table 2. Plant characteristics of VL Dhan 221 and Bala.

Character	VL Dhan 221	Bala (check)	Character	VL Dhan 221	Bala (check)
Plant height (cm)	90–95	65–70	Alkali digestion score ^b	2–3	2–3
Days to 50% flowering ^a	67–91	65–102	Gelatinization temperature ^b	Intermediate	Intermediate
Flag leaf	Erect	Erect	Amylose content ^b	Mid-High	Mid-High
Panicle type	Compact	Compact	Protein content ^b (%)	9.42	9.37
Panicle axis	Droopy	Droopy	Mineral ^b (%)	1.27	1.59
Awn type	Awnless	Awnless	Disease and insect pest reaction ^c		
Grain color	Straw	Straw	Leaf blast	4	5
1,000-grain wt (g)	22.7	17.2	Neck blast	3	7
Hulling percentage	71.4	71.8	Sheath rot	5	7
Grain length (mm)	8.23	6.47	Leaf scald	4	7
Grain width (mm)	2.81	2.88	Pink stem borer	5	5
Brown rice length (mm)	5.85	4.68	<i>Sesamia inferens</i>		
Brown rice width (mm)	2.49	2.40	Leafroller <i>Cnaphalocrocis</i> medinalis	5	7
Length:width	2.35	1.95			
Brown rice shape	Medium	Bold			
Volume expansion ^b	3.40	2.87			

^aRange at different locations over several years. ^bBased on brown rice. ^cMaximum score recorded using *Standard evaluation system for rice* (0–9) during 1985–87.

grow in 2 yr with a 150% cropping intensity. Regional farmers may be able to adopt a more economical rice-based cropping system (rice - wheat/barley/lentil/pea) with a 200% cropping intensity under rainfed conditions by cultivating VL Dhan 221, which is suitable for sowing in June. □

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Integrated germplasm improvement—deepwater

NDGR150 and NDGR151: two promising lines for semi-deepwater areas of eastern Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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Deepwater rice is grown on about 390,000 ha in eastern UP. About 2/3 of this area is under semi-deepwater conditions (50–100 cm) during the cropping period. Madhukar, Chakia 59, and local traditional varieties are currently cultivated in these areas. Suitable substitutes for these cultivars must be semitall and have good elongation ability, nonlodging plant type, photoperiod sensitivity, and high yield potential.

NDGR 150 and NDGR151 are sister lines from IET4060/Jalmagna. They are 135–175 cm (depending upon water depth) and have moderate tillering, kneeing, and elongation ability. They flower in late October, are photoperiod sensitive, and have well-exserted, compact panicles. Distinguishing traits include panicle lengths from 27 to 29 cm and 1,000-grain weights of 27.0–30.2 g. NDGR150 has white kernels; NDGR151, red kernels.

Table 1. Yield performance of promising lines and checks in station and in farmers' field trials. Ghagharaghat, UP, 1988–90.

Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	Station				32 farmers' fields			
	1988	1989	1990	Av	1988	1989	1990	Av
NDGR150	2.5	3.5	2.2	2.7	1.7	1.8	2.2	1.9
NDGR151	2.6	3.7	2.9	3.0	1.9	2.0	2.3	2.1
Sabita (national check)	1.7	2.9	2.1	2.1	1.5	1.4	2.1	1.6
Madhukar (local check)	1.4	2.2	1.1	1.5	1.6	0.9	1.5	1.3
Maximum water depth (cm)	65	52	45				45–95	

Table 2. Performance of promising lines and checks in regional and national trials in UP, 1987–90.^a

Site and year ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	NDGR150	NDGR151	Madhukar ^b	Sabita ^c	Tilakkachari ^c
<i>Adaptive trials</i>					
Bahraich					
1989 (56)	2.1	2.0	1.1	1.7	
1989 (51)	2.8	3.7	1.5	2.3	
Ballia					
1988 (45)	3.1	4.0	2.3	3.4	
1989 (75)	1.9	2.5	1.8	1.7	
Kuraumi					
1988 (60)	3.2	3.4	2.3	3.0	
1989 (100)	1.9	1.4	0.7	1.0	
<i>National trials</i>					
Faizabad, 1988 (37)	1.6	1.1	–	–	1.6
Pusa, 1988 (140)	3.8	0.6	–	–	(died)
Ghagharaghat 1988 (70)	1.6	1.9	–	–	1.1

^aMaximum water depths (cm) are in parentheses. ^bLocal check. ^cNational check.